

The Effect of Organic Acids and Graphene-Like Material on the Hydrolysis of Magnesium Hydride

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In recent years, special attention has been paid to the generation of hydrogen by the hydrolysis of various lightweight materials like ammonia borane [0], sodium borohydride [0], aluminium [0], magnesium hydride [0-0], and so on. These materials can undergo hydrolysis at near-ambient conditions, in alkaline or acidic medium.

Magnesium is an inexpensive, readily available and environment-friendly material, that makes it or its hydride a promising candidate for H₂ generation via hydrolysis, which, in case of MgH₂, takes place according to reaction:

Though the hydrolysis of MgH₂ starts immediately when in contact with water, it is quickly stagnated because of the formation of a passive magnesium hydroxide layer, which prevents diffusion of the water to the MgH₂ particles. To improve efficiency of MgH₂ hydrolysis, the main methods employed included carrying out the process in acidic medium [0,0], alloying with other metals [0], addition of chlorides [0] or ammonium salts [0], ball milling [0,0], addition of graphite [0,0], as well as ultra-sonication [0].

The present work focuses on the effect of organic acids (acetic, citric and oxalic) and nanoscale carbon (graphene-like material) on the hydrolysis of MgH₂, by dissolving the Mg(OH)₂ passivation layer to enhance the hydrolysis rate and H₂ generation yield. Use of the organic acids is economically feasible [0] and potentially has less environmental impact than that of mineral acids. Further improvement of hydrolysis performance was achieved by the addition of minor amounts of graphene-like material to MgH₂.

The hydrolysis of MgH₂ was performed in an H₂ generation reactor operated in a batch mode where the temperature and H₂ flow rate were logged. Different organic acid concentrations of 0 (deionized water), 1, 2, and 3 wt.% were used. The results (**Figure 1**) indicate that the addition of organic acids significantly increases the hydrolysis rate and H₂ yield, as compared to deionized water. The increase in the acid concentration leads to the increase in the reaction rate and yield of H₂. For the concentration of 3 wt.%, almost 100% H₂ yield was achieved in 3–5 minutes after reaction started (**Figure 1D**). The improvement of hydrolysis performance was associated with lowering pH of the aqueous solution (**Table I**) thus limiting formation of the Mg(OH)₂ passivation layer.

Figure 1: Curves of H₂ generation from MgH₂ at T=20 °C at different concentrations of organic acids 1, 2 and 3 wt. %, (A) Acetic Acid, (B) Citric Acid, (C) Oxalic Acid, (D) H₂ generation of MgH₂ in 3 wt. % organic acid solutions.

Table I: pH of MgH₂ solution before and after hydrolysis

	Water	Acetic Acid			Citric Acid			Oxalic Acid		
Acid concentration [wt. %]	0	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Initial pH	6.55	2.95	2.81	2.69	2.43	2.25	2.16	1.53	1.32	1.21
Final pH	11.04	5.54	5.28	4.28	5.32	4.98	4.53	4.84	3.32	2.11
H ₂ % yield after 5 min from reaction start	3.34	42.92	76.47	99.56	35.76	65.87	93.59	33.79	75.09	91.89

Composite of magnesium hydride with graphene-like material (MgH₂/GLM) was obtained by processing a mixture of magnesium with GLM in a planetary ball mill under hydrogen pressure of 30 atm [0]. Hydrolysis of the composite was performed using citric acid with concentrations of 0 (distilled water), 2 and 6 wt.%. The addition of GLM significantly increases the reaction rate of magnesium hydride with water compared to pure MgH₂: the reaction yield was 23.48% H₂ after 5 min. The addition of 2 and 6 wt.% citric acid significantly increases the H₂ yield: up to 69.18 and 94.94%, respectively. The maximum H₂ yield was achieved after 2-3 minutes from reaction start (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Curves of H₂ generation from MgH₂/GLM composite at T=20 °C at different concentrations of Citric Acid.

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